

First Steps Towards the Development of an LLM for the Cape Verdean Creole

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Abstract

This study presents a contribution to the development of a Large Language Model (LLM) for Cape Verdean Creole (CCV), with a particular focus on the fill-mask user task. Given the scarcity of linguistic resources and the dialectal diversity of CCV, the project presents considerable challenges, particularly in the creation and curation of a representative corpus. The adopted methodology includes the collection of corpora through crowdsourcing and web scraping, the development of tokenizers using Byte Pair Encoding, and the training and evaluation of DNN models. In one approach, we have trained from scratch with the collected corpora, a RoBERTa 83M-based model, and in another, we have fine-tuned Albertina 100M, a model pre-trained with European and Brazilian Portuguese. Various training and fine-tuning experiments were conducted on different computational infrastructures available at our university. The results show that the RoBERTa 83M-based model trained from scratch, with tokenization adapted to CCV, outperformed the fine-tuned Albertina 100M model (accuracy: 68.86%), due to its superior morphological compatibility with the target language. The study concludes that developing an LLM for CCV is both feasible and promising, representing a significant contribution to the processing of low-resource languages. Future work will focus on expanding the parallel corpus and extend the model to other downstream tasks.

Keywords — LLM, RoBERTa, Albertina, NLP, encoder, open-source, Cape Verdean Creole

I. INTRODUCTION

The present work contributes to the expanding ecosystem of Large Language Models (LLMs) tailored for underrepresented languages by introducing an encoder-based model specifically developed for Cape Verdean Creole (CCV). While the emergence of LLMs based on the Transformer architecture [1] has significantly advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) for high-resource languages, these advancements have not been equitably extended to linguistically underserved communities. Languages such as English, Portuguese, Spanish and other major European and Asian languages dominate the landscape of available open models [2], leaving languages like CCV without dedicated tools to support digital inclusion, education, e-commerce, and cultural preservation.

Despite the increasing availability of multilingual models – such as mBERT and XLM-R [3] - their performance often degrades in domains where training data is limited and morphosyntactic features are language-specific. Recent studies [2] show that adapting existing multilingual models through continued training on monolingual corpora, or developing dedicated monolingual models from scratch, can yield significant improvements for under-resourced languages [2][4].

Cape Verdean Creole poses unique challenges for NLP: its official use is emerging, and it is considered the mother language of the country since it is widely spoken. It comprises multiple dialects, and standardization efforts are underway. Additionally, there is a lack of digitized corpora for this language.

This paper is guided by two central research questions:

1. How might we develop a robust encoder-based LLM capable of processing Cape Verdean Creole, given the challenges of limited corpora availability and dialectal variation?
2. How might we assess the comparative effectiveness of LLM modeling via continued training versus training from scratch in the context of CCV?

To properly answer these research questions, we start by designing a data pipeline combining linguistic-led crowdsourced data collection and annotation, web scraping, and corpora curation, to build a set of monolingual CCV corpus and parallel corpora, including CCV-Portuguese and CCV- English.

The present work then explores two complementary machine learning modeling strategies: (1) fine-tuning a Portuguese encoder DNN model (Albertina 100M) [5] with CCV corpora, and (2) training from scratch a RoBERTa 83M-based DNN encoder model [6], where we also trained a tokenizer using the Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) algorithm [7], adapted to the specificities of the CCV language. The goal is to enable user tasks such as fill-masking (the ability of the model to predict a missing word), automatic translation, and text generation for CCV. Both models were quantitatively evaluated with standard literature metrics such as accuracy, F1 score, as well as qualitatively, with manual linguistic assessment.

II. RELATED WORK

The emergence of Transformer-based architectures [1] marked a paradigm shift in the field of NLP, enabling scalable and context-aware modeling of linguistic structures. This foundational breakthrough led to the development of high-performing encoder models such as BERT [9], RoBERTa [6], and DeBERTa [10], which remain state-of-the-art in various classification and text understanding tasks. However, these models have been predominantly trained on English corpora, offering limited support for low-resource or morphologically diverse languages. To promote and broaden linguistic inclusivity, multilingual models such as mBERT [3] were introduced, trained on datasets encompassing dozens of languages. Despite their broad applicability, these models tend to allocate a disproportional share of representational capacity to high-resource languages, resulting in suboptimal performance for underrepresented languages such as CCV. Moreover, the generic tokenization strategies employed often fail to capture the morphological idiosyncrasies of creole and local languages, thereby compromising linguistic fidelity. In response to these limitations, recent research has explored the development of language-specific or regionally adapted models. For instance, IndicBART [2] and AfriBERTa [3] were created to address Natural Language Generation and Natural Language Understanding tasks in Indic and African languages, respectively. These studies demonstrated that pre-training on linguistically similar languages or dialect groups – combined with tailored tokenization strategies – can significantly improve performance in low-resource contexts. The effectiveness of such models is further amplified when training corpora are aligned with the script, morphology, and phonology of the target language.

Within the Portuguese-speaking context, the Albertina encoder models [5] represent a significant milestone in open-source, high-performance NLP for both European (PT-PT) and Brazilian Portuguese (PT-BR). Trained on thousands of millions of tokens and based on the DeBERTa architecture, Albertina has achieved robust results in downstream tasks, including Recognizing Textual Entailment (RTE) and Semantic Textual Similarity (STS). Despite these advances, CCV remains critically underrepresented in the NLP research landscape. No publicly available encoder models have been specifically developed for CCV nor are there substantial benchmark datasets for this language, apart from very recent work [4], where the authors collected a variety of Creole languages corpora from countries of Latin America, Africa and the Caribbean, gathering 14.5M unique Creole sentences with parallel translations, totaling 11.6M for 41 languages, the first ever for 21, including CCV. In addition, the authors provide MT models supporting all 41 Creole languages in 172 translation directions, but not monolingual models. Other existing references to creole languages often rely on multilingual transfer or synthetic data generation, as seen in the AfroMT project [11].

To address this gap, the present work introduces a dedicated monolingual encoder model for Cape Verdean Creole, trained on a curated and crowdsourced corpus. By employing both fine-tuning (using Albertina 100M) and training from scratch (using RoBERTa 83M-like architecture), this study explores the trade-offs between leveraging existing linguistic proximity and models grounded in the specific linguistic features of CCV. This contribution represents one of the first structured efforts to develop encoder

models specifically for a creole language, aiming to establish a foundation for future research in under-resourced languages.

III. METHODS AND RESULTS

As mentioned, we adopted two distinct approaches in our modeling experiments. The first approach involved fine-tuning the pretrained 100M-parameter Albertina-based deep neural network (DNN) model for the fill-mask task, using our collected CCV corpus. The second approach consisted of training a RoBERTa 83M-based DNN model from scratch using the same corpus and targeting the same task.

A. Corpora

In this section, we present the corpora used for training and evaluating the encoder models. The dataset was collected from publicly available sources [4], as well as corpora provided by the linguistic group at the University of Cape Verde (UniCV), coordinated by Prof. Dominika Swolkien and Prof. Ana Karina. Data collection focused on the Santiago variant, which is the most resource-rich among the other CCV variants, a decision taken by the UniCV linguistic group.

The corpus was built through the following methods:

- Crowdsourcing via our specially developed web platform, where native speakers and a team of 3 professors of Linguistics and 6 CCV and Portuguese linguists, all from our partner institution of the UniCV, plus 1 linguist from ISCTE, contributed with corpora and validated aligned CCV-PT sentence pairs (see Fig. 1);
- Web scraping of Cape Verdean blogs, local news outlets, and community platforms containing publicly accessible CCV content, curated by the linguistics team of UniCV;
- Manual digitalization of public domain documents and historical texts provided by institutional partners of the UniCV;
- Manual validation by linguists and native speakers team, who curated, involving orthographic normalization, removal of redundant or low-quality content, and verification of grammatical consistency.

The final corpus used in this work contains over 781K sentences in Cape Verdean Creole, with more than 7.28M tokens, all curated through the aforementioned linguistically guided crowdsourced methodology. All documents were labeled into distinct categories. Table I presents the number of sentences per category.

The dataset was divided into three subsets: training, evaluation, and testing, following an 80%-10%-10% split, respectively. The purpose of each split is described as follows:

- Training dataset: Used for model training, this subset enables the model to learn patterns, relationships, and linguistic features from the data.
- Evaluation dataset: Used during the training process to fine-tune hyperparameters and determine optimal stopping points. This subset supports the selection of the best-performing model configuration prior to final testing.

- Testing dataset: Employed to assess the model’s performance on previously unseen data, this subset provides insights into generalization capability and helps identify potential overfitting.

FIG. 1 – CROWDSOURCING PLATFORM LANGUAGE EXPERT SCREEN

TABLE I – DATA SOURCE CATEGORIES AND SIZES IN THOUSANDS

Data Category	Sentences (K)
Jehovah Organization	458
General Documents	256
Media Articles	27
Stories	18
Web Scrapping	10
Music	9
Poetry	2
Children Stories	1

TABLE II – METRICS USED TO EVALUATE MODELS PERFORMANCE

Evaluation Method	Metric	Dataset Size (samples)
MLM on held-out set	Loss, Perplexity, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score	77 128
Human qualitative review	Manual Accuracy	250

B. Fine-tuning Albertina

Albertina 100M PT [12] was selected as the base model to explore the linguistic proximity between Portuguese and CCV. This encoder model, based on the DeBERTa architecture [10], was trained exclusively on Portuguese corpora (European and Brazilian Portuguese variants) and incorporates disentangled attention mechanisms, which enhances its ability to model complex syntactic and semantic relationships [10]. The model employs Byte-Level Byte-Pair Encoding (BPE) tokenization method and was pre-trained on a large Portuguese corpus, encompassing both the European (PT-PT) and Brazilian (PT-BR) variants. Given the grammatical and lexical overlap between CCV and Portuguese—particularly in vocabulary and syntactic structure—Albertina provides a solid foundation for transfer learning. Continued training (domain adaptation) was

performed using CCV corpora, targeting the fill-mask task, to create a Masked Language Model (MLM). This approach enables the model to retain its general Portuguese linguistic knowledge while adapting to the morphosyntactic

TABLE III – ALBERTINA 100M FINE-TUNE PERFORMANCE

Albertina 100M		
Sentence	Predicted Token	Confidence
<i>Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel <mask>?</i>	bes	0.542
	mon	0.1416
	li	0.0729
<i>Katxor sta trás di <mask>.</i>	el	0.2483
	es	0.1184
	la	0.0692

characteristics of CCV. Fine-tuning was conducted over 50 epochs using the training dataset, with its performance evaluated on the testing dataset. The original Albertina tokenization method was preserved, with no modifications applied.

Table II depicts the evaluation metrics used to assess the model’s performance.

Training was conducted over 50 epochs, with a total runtime of approximately 125 hours, utilizing the computational infrastructure provided by the ISCTE-Center for Technology Valorization and Transfer (CVTT) [13], which includes:

- 1x NVIDIA Ampere A100 80GB GPU
- 2x Intel Xeon Gold 6336Y) processors (24 cores each)
- 128 GB RAM
- 2 TB storage

The model architecture was configured with the following hyperparameters:

- Embedding size: 512
- Number of hidden layers: 12
- Number of attention heads: 12
- Batch size: 128
- Dropout rate: 0.1
- Weight decay: 0
- Adam epsilon: $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
- Learning rate: $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Two distinct evaluation strategies were employed:

1. Masked Language Modeling (MLM) evaluation: The models were assessed on a held-out subset of the CCV corpus (10%) using standard evaluation metrics, including Loss, Accuracy, F1-Score, Precision, and Recall;
2. Qualitative linguistic evaluation: Model outputs for the fill-mask task were manually reviewed by our linguists and native language team. Feedback was collected through a structured form-based interface deployed via Hugging Face Spaces (see Fig. 2).

FIG. 2 – HUGGING FACE SPACES MODEL TESTING PLATFORM

The metrics mentioned in the first approach are described by the following equations:

$$Accuracy_{Top1} = \frac{\text{Number of correct top predictions}}{\text{Total number of masked tokens}} \quad (1)$$

$$Precision = \frac{\text{Number of correct top1 predictions}}{\text{Total number of masked tokens}} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{\text{Number of correctly predicted masked tokens}}{\text{Total number of masked tokens}} \quad (3)$$

$$F1Score = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (4)$$

$$Loss = - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \cdot \log(\hat{y}_i) \quad (5)$$

Where y_i is the token ground truth of the testing dataset and \hat{y}_i is the token predicted by the model.

Fig. 3 illustrates the training dynamics of the Albertina 100M-based model, which simplified the assessment of overfitting, underfitting, and generalization behavior. Both training and evaluation loss curves showed strong convergence, with no signs of divergence between them. Around epoch 40, the losses began to stabilize, reaching approximately 0.60 for the training loss and 0.69 for the evaluation loss. This plateau suggests that the model has achieved its optimal performance under the given training conditions, and further training with the same corpus and hyperparameters would likely yield marginal or no additional improvements.

After 50 training epochs, the model achieved the following evaluation metrics:

- Accuracy: 0.6726
- F1-Score: 0.6550
- Recall: 0.6726
- Precision: 0.6874
- Evaluation loss: 2.1913

FIG. 3 – ALBERTINA 100M LOSS EVOLUTION OVER 50 EPOCHS

C. Training RoBERTa from scratch

A RoBERTa 83M-based DNN encoder model was trained from scratch, using the CCV training dataset. RoBERTa [6] is a robustly optimized variant of BERT that removes the Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) objective and introduces dynamic masking and extended training schedules. This architecture has demonstrated strong performance for low-resource languages, particularly when combined with a language-specific tokenizer. To accommodate CCV's unique morphological complexity and orthographic variation, a new BPE tokenizer was trained directly on the CCV corpora. BPE is a sub-word tokenization algorithm that enables effective handling of out-of-vocabulary and rare terms by decomposing them into known sub-word units, thus balancing character-level and word-level representations. A vocabulary size of 52,000 unique tokens was defined to build a comprehensive lexicon for CCV. Notably, punctuation and whitespace characters were retained during preprocessing to preserve CCV-specific morphemes and prevent over-fragmentation due to limited frequency statistics. The tokenizer was evaluated through fill-mask task.

The model was trained over 200 epochs, with a total training time of approximately 223 hours, using the same computational infrastructure previously described for the Albertina model [13]. The training configuration was defined by the following hyperparameters:

- Embedding size: 768
- Number of hidden layers: 6
- Number of attention heads: 12
- Batch size: 128
- Dropout rate: 0.1
- Weight decay: 0
- Adam epsilon: $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$
- Learning rate: $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$

The model was evaluated using the same methodologies and metrics of sub-section III.B (Fine-Tuning Albertina).

Fig. 4 illustrates the training dynamics of the model, enabling the assessment of potential overfitting, underfitting, or effective generalization. In this case, the model demonstrated consistent convergence, with both training and evaluation losses decreasing steadily. Notably, the evaluation loss closely followed the training loss throughout the process, with no signs of divergence, indicating the absence of overfitting. Around epoch 170, both losses began to stabilize, reaching approximately 1.08 for the training loss and 1.60 for the evaluation loss, which indicated that the model had reached a plateau in performance. Consequently, further

training was unlikely to yield significant improvements, with the same hyperparameters and dataset.

The model achieved the following performance in the MLM metrics:

- Accuracy: 0.6877
- F1-score: 0.6766
- Precision: 0.6819
- Recall: 0.6877
- Evaluation loss: 1.5996

FIG. 4 – ROBERTA 83M LOSS EVOLUTION OVER 200 EPOCHS

IV. DISCUSSION

This section presents, discusses, and compares the performance of the models introduced in Section III. Albertina 100M fine-tuned for CCV.

The model achieved satisfactory performance across standard evaluation metrics. An accuracy of 0.6726 indicates that it correctly predicted the masked tokens in 67.26% of the test instances, selecting from a vocabulary of 50,264 unique tokens.

Regarding the qualitative evaluation, 250 sentences generated by our MLM were evaluated by a linguist. Out of these, 67 errors were identified. These errors are mostly related to syntactic structure and morphology, with the model struggling to construct well-formed phrases.

Table III. presents some results of the tests conducted by the linguist with the corresponding predicted token and confidence of the model.

Given the following input “Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel <mask>?” our model generated three predicted token hypotheses, by order of confidence, presented in Table III:

Output 1: “Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel bes?”

In this instance, the model took the sentence “Where is that pan that I gave you that” and predicted the word “time” (bes) resulting in “Where is that pan that I gave you that time”, which was considered well-formed by the linguist.

Output 2: “Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel mon?”

Here, the model predicted the token “hand” (mon) resulting in “Where is that pan that I gave you that hand”. This output does not make sense according to the linguist, showing that the model is struggling to capture the context and fill with a good word.

Output 3: Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel li?

The third token predicted corresponds to the word “here” (li), finishing the sentence with “Where is that pan that I gave you that here”. According to the linguist, the model failed to fill with a good token.

The following example illustrates another performance assessment conducted by the linguist. The input “Katxor sta trás di <mask>.” generated another three hypotheses for evaluation, ordered by the same confidence described above, presented in the Table III.

Output 1: Katxor sta trás di el.

Regarding this sentence “The dog is behind the <mask>”, the model predicts the word “he” (el) resulting in “The dog is behind him”. In this case, the linguist confirmed that the model was able to complete this task.

Output 2: Katxor sta trás di es.

The next output the model predicted the word “they” (es) resulting in “The dog is behind them”. This token is also a good prediction according to the linguist.

Output 3: Katxor sta trás di la.

The third output, with the third highest score is “there” (la), resulting in “The dog is behind there”. The replacement of <mask> with the token “la” (there) is a syntactic mismatch, as stated by the linguist.

Despite completing the fill-mask task, the model exhibited certain difficulties, as demonstrated by the examples above and the error rates reported in the linguistics evaluations. The tests conducted by linguists revealed that the model requires more data and further training. A significant number of Portuguese words were observed in its predictions, likely due to its pre-training on Portuguese. Additionally, the tokenizer used, Byte Level Byte Pair Encoding, follows a sub-word frequency approach like BPE, which results in excessive word splitting due to its previous training on a different language. Therefore, the model’s predicted tokens often average only 2–3 characters in length.

TABLE IV – ROBERTA 83M PERFORMANCE

<i>RoBERTa 83M</i>		
Sentence	Predicted Token	Confidence
<i>Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel <mask>?</i>	kumida	0.7595
	káldu	0.0412
	kafé	0.0145
<i>Katxor sta trás di <mask>.</i>	kása	0.3909
	kural	0.1461
	lumi	0.0941

Regarding the RoBERTa 83M model, the results obtained in standard metrics evaluation indicate that, despite its reduced complexity in terms of parameter count and reduced corpora,

the model attained satisfactory performance across standard evaluation metrics. An accuracy score of 0.6877 demonstrates that the model correctly predicts the masked token in 68.77% of the test instances, where each prediction requires choosing from a vocabulary consisting of approximately 52,000 unique tokens (vocabulary size).

The same set of 250 Creole sentences were used in our RoBERTa-based model evaluation. Out of the 250 sentences, errors were identified in 12 sentences. These errors were related to the contextual appropriateness of the sentences; that is, while the phrases were grammatically well-constructed, the inserted words did not semantically fit the given context.

The next examples describe this qualitative evaluation approach. The input “Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel <mask>?” generated three predicted token hypotheses, by order of confidence, presented in Table IV:

Output 1: Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel **kumida**?

The model predicted “*food*” (kumida) as the masked token, resulting in: “Where is that pan that I gave you with the food.” This result demonstrates the model’s ability to predict a good token aligned with the structural expectations of the language while attending contextual cues, accordingly to the linguist.

Output 2: Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel **káldu**?

The predicted token is “broth” (káldu), transforming the sentence into “Where is that pan that I gave you with the broth”. This sentence is aligned with contextual meaning and grammar.

Output 3: Undi ki sta kel panéla ki N dá-u kel **kafé**?

The last predicted token is “coffee” (kafé), being the final sentence “Where is that pan that I gave you with coffee”. This token also makes sense in the sentence, since a pan can carry coffee.

The input “Katxor sta trás di <mask>.” is the same example used in Albertina discussion, generating another three different hypothesis (see Table IV):

Output 1: Katxor sta trás di **kása**.

The corresponding translation is: “The dog is behind the <mask>”, with the model’s output rendering “The dog is behind the house”. In this instance, the model correctly predicted the masked token with a word that aligns with the contextual meaning of the sentence.

Output 2: Katxor sta trás di **kural**.

The second prediction is “corral” (Kural), resulting in “The dog is behind the corral”. This prediction is aligned with the context of the sentence too.

Output 3: Katxor sta trás di **lumi**.

The third prediction is “fire” (lumi) resulting in “The dog is behind the fire”. This last prediction is also aligned with the context of the sentence.

These outcomes demonstrate the RoBERTa-based model’s intended behavior: its ability to predict missing tokens attending to sentence structure and contextual information. The preliminary tests conducted by the linguist reinforced our confidence in the model’s performance

assessed by our MLM evaluation. Although the findings are promising, we clearly need to continue our data collection efforts to access and curate more diverse data and proceed with further model training and testing.

A. Model’s Comparison

Our models were trained for the fill-mask task. The RoBERTa 83M-based DNN model outperformed the fine-tuned version of the Albertina 100M-based model in both standard evaluation metrics and linguistic testing. Despite Albertina having a higher number of parameters (100 million vs. 83 million) and being pre-trained on a larger European and Brazilian Portuguese corpora, it was less effective at capturing the specific linguistic patterns of Cape Verdean Creole.

Albertina was developed by continuing the training of the DeBERTa [10] model, which was originally trained on English and subsequently adapted for European and Brazilian Portuguese. As a result, the model inherits linguistic patterns and tokenization strategies that are not fully aligned with Cape Verdean Creole. Due to the significant structural and grammatical differences between this Creole language and the languages used during earlier training stages, the model struggles to effectively capture the linguistic nuances of this language.

Our RoBERTa 83M-based model, on the other hand demonstrated that training a tokenizer from scratch specifically for the target languages (CCV) leads to improved results, as it captures the language’s unique structure more effectively. As a result, this approach reduces the number of sub-word splits required to represent individual words, allowing each token to retain more semantic meaning. The chosen tokenizer for our RoBERTa 83M-based model was BPE, due to its flexibility to unseen tokens. In contrast, the fine-tuning of the Albertina model retained the original tokenizer used in DeBERTa. This mismatch between the tokenizer and the target language contributed to the Albertina-100M based model lower performance, as it was less capable of representing the linguistic nuances of Creole. This confirms the conclusion addressed above in the individual model discussion, of Section IV.A.

It is noteworthy that tokenizers of pre-trained models cannot be changed, because they are tightly coupled with the model architecture and its training data. This change would result in a mismatch between the pre-trained model’s vocabulary and its input IDs which would no longer correspond to valid embeddings.

TABLE V – ALBERTINA 100M & ROBERTA 83M METRICS COMPARISON

Metric	Albertina 100M	RoBERTa 83M
Accuracy	0.6726	0.6877
F1-score	0.6550	0.6766
Recall	0.6726	0.6877
Precision	0.6874	0.6819
Evaluation Loss	2.1913	1.5996
Linguistic Errors	67	12

Although the qualitative results obtained by the RoBERTa-based model are overall better than by Albertina fine-tuning, the differences in standard metrics are small. The accuracy is modest, but it is the first published figures of such metrics to the best of the authors knowledge therefore setting the baseline for the community regarding other Cape Verdean creole models. When evaluated by the linguistic, the changes became more significant: RoBERTa has 12 sentences with errors out of 250 and Albertina has 67 sentences with errors in the same sample space.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

To the best of the authors knowledge, this paper presents the world's first monolingual encoder-based LLM of the Cape Verdean Creole language and its evaluation results.

Our team started by collecting CCV corpora from a range of publicly available sources via a close collaboration with linguist professors and students from the University of Cape Verde and the Bridgewater State University.

Our modeling approach comprised two strategies. In the first one we fine-tuned an already existing European and Brazilian PT model (Albertina 100M), and in the second, we trained from scratch a RoBERTa 83M-based model, both with our available corpus. Training took place in the newly inaugurated high-performance computing center of ISCTE-Center for Technology Valorization and Transfer (CVTT).

Both models were evaluated using two approaches. In the first one, MLM evaluation revealed the superiority of the RoBERTa 83M-based model in a fill-mask task, as measured by accuracy, F1-score, Recall and evaluation loss. Qualitative evaluation showed that again, the RoBERTa 83M-based model outperformed Albertina's in real fill-mask test cases, as assessed by our linguist, which found only 12 errors in 250 sentences generated by RoBERTa's model, compared to 67 errors found in the Albertina case.

Future work will focus on training and evaluating existing models, as well as exploring multilingual architectures like mBERT and XLM-R, with a larger, more diverse, and high-quality CCV corpora. Although the current models have achieved satisfactory performance, we believe that expanding and strengthening the dataset will lead to further improvements in accuracy and generalization. This enhancement will be a key step toward developing more complex downstream models, particularly for tasks such as machine translation and question answering. In addition, the models will be made publicly available in Hugging Face to support transparency and encourage further research in the community.

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